

Synthesis and Growth Retardant Activities of Trialkylammonium Iodides from Piperonal and β -Naphthol

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N,N-Dimethyl-2-(β -naphthoxy)ethanamine (4), *N,N*-dimethyl-2-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenoxy)ethanamine (4b), *N,N*-diethyl-2-(β -naphthoxy)ethanamine (8a), *N,N*-diethyl-2-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenoxy)ethanamine (8b) and *N,N*-dimethyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)prop-2-enamine (15) have been prepared and converted into the corresponding quaternary salts of ammonia by treating them with methyl and ethyl iodides. The compounds have been tested as plant growth inhibitors on *Brassica juncea*.

IN continuation of our work on the syntheses of new plant growth retardants¹⁻³, we report here the preparation of ten new trialkylammonium compounds with piperonal and β -naphthol moiety and tested their biological activity on raya seeds (Table 1).

Chart 1

Chart 2

N,N-Dimethyl-2-(β -naphthoxy)ethanamide (3a) was prepared from β -naphthoxyacetic acid (1a) by

reacting its acid chloride with aqueous solution of dimethylamine⁴. Similarly, *N,N*-dimethyl-2-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenoxy)ethanamide (3b) was prepared from 3,4-methylenedioxyphenoxyacetic acid (1b). The amides (3a and 3b) were then subjected to LAH reduction in dry ether to get *N,N*-dimethyl-2-(β -naphthoxy)aminoethane (4a) and *N,N*-dimethyl-2-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenoxy)aminoethane (4b), respectively. β -Naphthol and 3,4-methylenedioxyphenol were also converted to their *N,N*-diethyl-amino-derivatives (8a and 8b) as follows.

Phenols were converted to 2-(β -naphthoxy)-bromoethane (7a) and 2-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenoxy)bromoethane (7b) by heating them with aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide and ethylene bromide⁵. The aryloxy bromides (7a and 7b) were then converted to *N,N*-diethyl-2-(β -naphthoxy)aminoethane (8a) and *N,N*-diethyl-2-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenoxy)aminoethane (8b), respectively, by refluxing them with diethylamine and anhydrous K₂CO₃ in dry acetone⁶.

N,N-Dimethyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-prop-2-enylamine (15) was prepared from piperonal. Piperonal was converted to piperonyl acrylic acid (12) by its reaction with aqueous NaOH and malonic acid⁷. The acid (12) was then converted first to *N,N*-dimethyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-prop-2-enylamide (14) and then reduced with LAH in dry ether as described above⁴. Its pmr spectrum gave doublets at δ 6.98 and 7.7 (J 15Hz) establishing the (*E*)-geometry of double bond. The trialkylamines (4a, 4b, 8a, 8b and 15) were then converted to their corresponding quaternary ammonium compounds (5a, 5b, 6a, 6b, 9a, 9b, 10a, 10b, 16 and 18) by treating them with methyl and ethyl iodides in dry ether.

The compounds were tested on raya (*Brassica juncea*) and percent germination and average root lengths were measured by taking different concentrations. No definite conclusions were drawn in the case of germination but from the root lengths,

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATION OF COMPOUNDS ON THE NUMBER OF SEEDS AFTER 5 DAYS

Compd. no.	% Germination				Average root length in conc.			
	50 ppm	20 ppm	10 ppm	5 ppm	50 ppm	20 ppm	10 ppm	5 ppm
5a	64	60	64	80	7.49	6.04	6.99	5.72
5b	64	56	72	80	2.8	6.8	5.9	6.6
6a	76	64	72	60	8.6	6.05	8.15	6.2
6b	48	52	80	68	3.05	4.25	8.5	6.65
9a	68	80	88	64	8.08	7.5	9.2	6.7
9b	68	76	84	72	6.22	6.7	6.65	6.0
10a	84	84	92	92	8.15	9.6	7.8	9.62
10b	60	56	92	88	7.8	7.95	7.85	8.4
16	72	92	80	68	5.4	10.2	9.4	8.82
17	100	72	84	68	9.0	10.0	6.95	9.85
Control			87%			7.95		

the compounds 5b, 6a and 9b showed inhibition properties whereas other compounds gave no definite information.

Experimental

B.ps. and m.ps. are uncorrected. Unless otherwise stated all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 , and purity of samples was checked by tlc. Nmr spectra (90 MHz; CCl_4) were recorded on a EM 360/390 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

N,N-Dimethyl-2-(β -naphthoxy)ethanamide (3a) : A mixture of 2-(β -naphthoxy)ethanoic acid (3.00 g) and thionyl chloride (4.5 ml) was kept at room temperature for 16 h. Excess thionylchloride was then removed and the residue distilled to yield the acid chloride (2a) as a colourless liquid (2.8 g, 93%).

To the ice-cooled aqueous methylamine (38% ; 20 ml) acid chloride (2a, 2.8 g) dissolved in dry benzene (20 ml) was added dropwise in 0.5 h with stirring. Stirring was continued for another 4 h at 4° and the mixture left at room temperature for overnight. It was then diluted with water (100 ml) and the benzene layer separated. The aqueous part extracted with benzene (5 × 500 ml) and the combined organic extract was washed with 10% aqueous KOH (25 ml) followed by water. After drying the extract over sodium sulphate solvent was removed. Distillation of the residue gave the amide (3a) as a light brown liquid, which solidified on cooling (2.3 g, 84%), m.p. 28–30° ; δ 2.96, 3.0 (3H each, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 4.7 (2H, s, Ar-O-CH₂) and 7.2–7.86 (7H, m, ArH).

N,N-Dimethyl-2-(β -naphthoxy)aminoethane (4a) : The dimethylamide (3a ; 2.0 g) in dry ether (50 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred slurry of LAH (1.0 g) in dry ether (100 ml) at room temperature. After stirring for 16 h, the mixture was cooled, treated successively with water (1.3 ml), 15% aqueous NaOH (1.3 ml) and water (3.9 ml) and stirred again for another 15 min. The organic layer was separated, aqueous layer washed with more ether and the combined ether extract was dried with sodium sulphate. Removal of solvent followed by distillation of the residue gave the amine as a dark brown

liquid, b.p. 90–2°/8–9 mm (Found C, 78.08 ; H, 7.98 ; N, 6.57. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{ON}$ requires : C, 78.13 ; H, 7.90 ; N, 6.5%) ; δ 2.12 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.92 (2H, t, J 8Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.96 (2H, t, J 8Hz, OCH_2) and 6.64–8.2 (7H, m, ArH).

N,N-Dimethyl-2-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenoxy)-aminoethane (4b) : Piperonal (5.75 g) and chloroacetic acid (4 g) were mixed and melted on a water-bath. A solution of sodium hydroxide (6N, 20 ml) was then added to it slowly with stirring. Stirring and heating was continued for 3 h. The cooled reaction mixture was diluted with water (50 ml) and acidified with concentrated HCl to give brick-red solid (4.53 g, 79%), m.p. 116–18°. The acid (1b) was converted to the title compound (4b) through the formation of the amide (3b) as described above, (70%) b.p. 85–7°/5–6 mm (Found : C, 63.20 ; H, 7.12 ; N, 6.74. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires : C, 63.15 ; H, 7.17 ; N, 6.69%) ; δ 2.3 (3H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.75 (2H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.9 (2H, t, J 7Hz, OCH_2), 5.92 (2H, s, OCH_2O) and 6.72 (3H, m, ArH).

N,N-Diethyl-2-(β -naphthoxy)aminoethane (8a) : To a mixture of β -naphthol (4.1 g) and ethylene bromide (6.7 g), 10% NaOH was added slowly with stirring and refluxed for 6 h at 120° on an oil-bath. The cooled reaction mixture was extracted with benzene. The extract was washed with 2N NaOH and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent gave the bromide (8a ; 3.0 g, 70%).

A mixture of the bromoethane (7a ; 3 g), diethylamine (1 g) and K_2CO_3 (1.5 g) was refluxed with acetone at 60° for 6 h. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered and most of the acetone removed by distillation. Water (15 ml) was then added and the solution was extracted with ether. Ether extract was dried over Na_2SO_4 . Removal of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation gave the amine (8a ; 1.7 g, 52%), b.p. 102–03°/7–8 mm (Found : C, 79.1 ; H, 8.71 ; N, 5.72. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{ON}$ requires : C, 79.01 ; H, 8.64 ; N, 5.76%) ; δ 1.16 (6H, t, J 8Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.78 (4H, q, J 8Hz, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3)_2$), 3.1 (2H, t, J 7Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$), 4.34 (2H, t, J 7Hz, OCH_2) and 6.92–8.46 (7H, m, ArH).

N,N-Diethyl-2-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenoxy)-aminoethane (8b) : It was prepared according to the procedure described above, (52%), b.p. 90–2°/

6–7 mm (Found: 65.76; H, 7.97; N, 5.94. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2N$ requires: C, 65.82; H, 8.01; N, 5.90%); δ 1.1 (6H, t, J 8Hz, $N(CH_2CH_2)_2$), 2.4 (4H, q, J 8Hz, $N(CH_2CH_2)_2$), 2.78 (2H, t, J 7Hz, $CH_2N(CH_2CH_2)_2$), 3.9 (2H, t, J 7Hz, OCH_2), 5.9 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.20 (2H, m, ArH) and 7.32 (1H, s, ArH).

N,N-Dimethyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)prop-2-enamide (14): A mixture of piperonal (5 g), malonic acid (7.5 g), pyridine (15 ml) and traces of piperidine was refluxed for 1 h. After cooling, it was poured into excess water containing enough HCl to react with pyridine. It was then filtered, washed with water and dried to give the unsaturated acid (12; 6 g, 86%), m.p. 236°.

The acid (12) was then converted to the amide (14) through its acid chloride formation according to the procedure followed in 3b, (1.3 g, 99%), m.p. 118°; δ 3.15 (6H, brs, $CON(CH_2)_2$), 6.03 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.75–7.15 (3H, m, ArH), 6.98 (1H, d, J 15Hz, ArCH=CH) and 7.7 (1H, d, J 15Hz, ArCH=CH).

N,N-Dimethyl-3-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)prop-2-enamine (15): It was prepared according to the procedure described in 4a, b.p. 110–12°/5–6 mm (Found: C, 70.30; H, 7.27; N, 6.75. $C_{15}H_{15}O_2N$ requires: C, 70.24; H, 7.31; N, 6.82%); δ 2.1 (6H, s, $N(CH_2)_2$), 2.88 (2H, d, J 7Hz, $CH_2N(CH_2)_2$), 5.88 (2H, s, OCH_2O), 6.35 (1H, d, J 15Hz, ArCH

=CH), 6.7 (3H, brs, ArH) and 6.78 (1H, d, J 15Hz, ArCH=CH).

Quaternary ammonium compounds (5a, b, 6a, b, 9a, b, 10a, b, 16 and 17): To a solution of 4a (0.5 g) in dry ether (10 ml), methyl iodide (0.5 ml) was added and the reaction mixture stirred for 2 h and then left overnight at room temperature. The resulting white solid trimethylammonium iodide (5a) was filtered, (0.7 g, 85%), m.p. 160–61° (Found: C, 50.51; H, 5.60; N, 3.92. $C_{15}H_{20}ONI$ requires: C, 50.42; H, 5.60; N, 3.92%).

Similarly, other quaternary salts of ammonia were prepared in more than 80% yield. Except compounds 9a (m.p. 62–4°) all other compounds were found to be hygroscopic in nature.

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